

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE DRILLING OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS ON THE MACROSCOPIC AND MICROSCOPIC SCALES

Fuji Wang¹, Xiaonan Wang, Zhenyuan Jia, Rao Fu, Yu Bai and Youliang Su

¹ The Key Laboratory for Precision and Nontraditional Machining Technology of Ministry of Education, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian 116024, China, E-mail: wfjsll@dlut.edu.cn, web page: <http://www.dlut.edu.cn/>

Keywords: Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics, Simulation, Drilling, Burr, Fiber

ABSTRACT

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs) are a kind of hard-to-machine material. They are vulnerable to the generation of delamination, burring, fiber-matrix debonding and etc. during the drilling process. The drilling induced delamination has been researched in some previous studies. Whereas, the burring, fiber-matrix debonding that critical to the structural strength of the workpiece and the assembly of the components are rarely studied. The objective of this paper is to study the burrs induced in the drilling of CFRP laminates. Considering the numerical simulation has great advantages for the study of the damage induced by CFRP drilling, a three-dimensional finite element model was developed to simulate the drilling of multi-directional CFRPs. As the CFRPs consist of fiber phase and matrix phase on microscopic scale and exhibit anisotropy and stacking features on macroscopic scale, the model was developed on both of the two scales. In this model, part of the workpiece contains fiber phase and matrix phase to simulate the CFRP drilling on microscopic scale. (It should be noted that, the fiber phase is not representing a single fiber, but a bundle of fibers due to computational constraints.) And the other part was modelled based on the Equivalent Homogeneous Material (EHM) assumption to simulate the CFRP drilling on macroscopic scale. Meanwhile, the size of the elements in different parts were unequal, and a balance between accuracy and computational cost was achieved through refining the element sizes. Also, different constitutive laws, failure initiation criteria and damage evolution laws were implemented to replicate the interrelated cutting behaviour of different phases. The drilling process of the multi-directional CFRPs was simulated by this model, and the sizes of the induced burrs at the hole wall and outlet of the hole were compared. In addition, the simulation results were validated by experiments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs) possess the advantages of high strength-to-weight ratio and high modulus-to-weight ratio. These properties make CFRPs widely used in aerospace, transportation and energy applications [1-3]. However, the CFRP laminates consist of fiber phase and matrix phase on microscopic scale. The mechanical properties of the two phases are different, and the strength of the fibers are high thus they are difficult to remove. Also, the CFRPs exhibit anisotropy and stacking features on macroscopic scale, and the interlaminar bond strength of the workpiece is weak [4]. Therefore, serious damage such as burring, fiber-matrix debonding and delamination are induced easily during the drilling of CFRP components [5-7].

The induced damage can not only reduce the quality of the processed surface of the workpiece badly, but also reduce the structural strength and the bearing capacity of the CFRPs seriously. And then, it will cause great assembly error, and short the service life of the components [8]. Therefore, it is necessary to study the burring, fiber-matrix debonding and delamination so as to suppression them. Researching the damage experimentally is expensive in terms of time and cost, and the presence of fibers in the chip are potentially harmful to experimenters [9]. Meanwhile, the analysis of the burring and fiber-matrix debonding requires clear observations of the CFRP drilling, which are difficult under current experimental conditions. However, the drilling process can be observed from different scales conveniently by numerical simulation, which can help the analysis of the induced damage without the

cost problem of experiments [10]. Nevertheless, a real simulation of the CFRP drilling requires the definition of the material behaviours and the boundary conditions, and a balance should be found between the simulate precision and computational efficiency.

Recently, researchers have did a series of studies on the drilling of CFRP laminates through numerical simulation, but mainly focused on the delamination by macro mechanical models that based on the Equivalent Homogenous Material (EHM) assumption. Isbilir et. al [11-12] developed a macro mechanical model for the drilling of CFRPs based on the theory of Hashin and the cohesive element. The model was used to study the effect of stage ratios of step drill on delamination, and it could help to guide the design of the drill geometry. Phadnis et. al [13-14] researched the effect of drilling parameters on the initiation and propagation of the delamination by the simulation of the CFRP drilling on macroscopic scale. And the model was also used to optimize the feed rate and cutting speed to mitigate the drilling-induced damage. Feito et. al [15-16] developed both the simplified model and the complete model for the CFRP drilling. The simplified model which assuming that the drill acts like a punch that pierces through the laminates was used to study the influence of the thrust force and the stacking sequence on delamination. And the complete model which including feed and rotation movements of the drill was used for the study of the delamination under different tool geometrys and drilling parameters.

However, with the continuous development of the CFRPs, the strength of the fibers contained in them are higher and higher. Which makes the fibers are more difficult to remove, such as T800 fibers. Besides, the abrasion resistance of these fibers are also very high. Thus, the fibers will exacerbate the wear of the tools, which is not conducive to the cutting off of the fibers [17-19]. Consequently, the burring and fiber-matrix debonding are induced more serious during the CFRP drilling, as shown in Figure 1. However, there are few studies focusing on the burring and fiber-matrix debonding, which is related to the cutting behaviours of the fibers and matrix on microscopic scale. In order to research the burring and fiber-matrix debonding deeply, a multiscale simulation model of the CFRP drilling need to be developed.

Figure 1: Burring and fiber-matrix debonding induced by CFRP drilling

For a real simulation of the CFRP drilling on different scales, the material behaviours should be defined according to the features of the workpiece. The CFRPs containing fiber phase and matrix phase on microscopic scale. And the fiber phase and matrix phase have drastically different mechanical properties, also there were complex interactions happened between them during drilling. Therefore, different constitutive laws, failure initiation criteria and damage evolution laws need to be applied to replicate the interrelated cutting behaviour of different phases. Meanwhile, the material behaviour of the CFRPs on macroscopic scale should also be defined respectively. Additionally, these material behaviours must be compiled into reasonable procedure to do the simulation.

Despite the computing power has advanced greatly in recent years, the simulation of the CFRP drilling still takes very long time. For example, the simulation time for the model developed by Feito et. al ranged from 4 days to 3 weeks in a workstation [15]. Due to the quantity and size of the elements of the model have large influence on the simulation time, the model must be simplified to improve the computational efficient. Otherwise, the multiscale simulation model cannot be calculated in a limited

time and the study of the damage cannot be carried out. And it is an effective simplify method to set a small fiber-matrix combined part in the model for the simulation on microscopic scale, and set the other part of the model to be EHM for the simulation on macroscopic scale.

In this paper, a simulation model was established on both the macroscopic and microscopic scales firstly. The model including the micro part and the macro part. In which, the micro part containing the fiber phase and matrix phase was used to simulate the CFRP drilling on microscopic scale, and the macro part that set to be Equivalent Homogeneous Material (EHM) was used to simulate the CFRP drilling on macroscopic scale. And different material behaviours were applied to characterize the properties of the phases included in the two parts. Then, the drilling process of the multi-laminate CFRPs were simulated through this model. After that, drilling experiments were performed and the results of the finite element simulation and the experiments were compared for validation purpose. Finally, the burrs induced in the drilling of the multi-laminate CFRPs were analyzed.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

2.1 Material modelling

In this paper, the finite element model contains fiber phase, matrix phase and EHM. Wherein the material properties of the fiber phase and the EHM were assumed to be orthotropic. And isotropic material properties were assigned to the matrix phase. In order to simulate the drilling process of CFRP laminates, the constitutive laws, failure initiation criteria and damage evolution laws for each phases were required.

2.1.1 Material behaviour of the EHM and the fiber phase

Considering the orthotropic material properties of the fiber phase and the EHM, the material behaviour of them in the longitudinal direction and the transverse direction were defined to be different. Linear elastic material behaviour was assumed to the fiber phase and the EHM until failure:

$$\sigma_i = C_{ij} \varepsilon_j \quad (1)$$

The failure initiation criteria that including different failure modes were based on the theory of Hashin. When implement the stress-based Hashin criteria in a numerical routine, the dramatic varying stresses due to degradation of material properties may cause numerical instability [20]. To avoid this problem, a strain-based Hashin criteria that applied by Yang et. al [20] was used in this paper. When the failure index F reaches 1, it means that the corresponding mode of failure is initiated and the damage occurs.

If failure is detected, the element stiffness begins to degrade and the effective elasticity matrix is reduced according to the exponential damage evolution law in this paper. In another word, when the failure initiation criteria is satisfied, the damage variables d starts to increase from 0. When d approaches a value of one, it is indicated that the stiffness of the element is degrades to zero, and the element will be deleted. The calculation of the damage variables d was also based on the study of Yang et. al [20]

The material behaviour of the EHM and the fiber phase were implemented into the finite element software Abaqus/explicit by a user-defined material model (VUMAT), and the element deletion during the simulation was also controlled by a state variable defined in the VUMAT. The material properties of the EHM and the fiber phase are shown in Table 1.

Material properties		EHM	Fiber
Elastic modulus	E_1 (GPa)	178	294
	$E_2=E_3$ (GPa)	9.5	15
Shear modulus	$G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	6.33	103
	G_{23} (GPa)	4.21	89
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.29	0.25
	ν_{23}	0.37	0.28
Longitudinal tensile strength	X_T (MPa)	2950	5880

Longitudinal compressive strength	X _C (MPa)	1553	3850
Transverse tensile strength	Y _T (MPa)	117	225
Transverse compressive strength	Y _C (MPa)	350	600
Shear strength	S(MPa)	144	140
Density	ρ(g/cm ³)	1530	1800

Table 1: The material properties of the EHM and the fiber phase

2.1.2 Material behaviour of the matrix phase

The material properties of the matrix phase were assumed to be isotropic in this paper. Elastic-plastic material behaviour was assigned to the matrix phase until failure, wherein the isotropic plastic hardening was used.

The failure initiation criteria for the matrix phase was the shear criteria in this paper:

$$\omega_s = \int \frac{d\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_s^{pl}(\theta_s, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^{pl})} = 1 \quad (4)$$

Where, ω_s is the failure index, $\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}$ is the equivalent plastic strain, $\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ is the equivalent plastic strain rate, $\bar{\varepsilon}_s^{pl}$ is a function of the shear stress ratio and strain rate, $\theta_s = (q + k_s p) / \tau_{max}$ is the shear stress ratio, q is the Mises equivalent stress, p is the pressure stress, k_s is a material parameter, τ_{max} is the maximum shear stress.

In addition, a linear evolution of the damage variable with plastic displacement was applied. Then, once the failure initiation criterion was met, the damage variable d increases according to formula (5). The model ensured that the energy dissipated during the damage evolution process was equal to the fracture energy per unit area.

$$\dot{d} = \frac{L^c \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^{pl}}{\bar{u}_f^{pl}} = \frac{\dot{\bar{u}}^{pl}}{\bar{u}_f^{pl}} \quad (5)$$

Where, the equivalent plastic displacement at damage \bar{u}_f^{pl} is computed as

$$\bar{u}_f^{pl} = \frac{2G_f}{\sigma_{y0}} \quad (6)$$

In which, σ_{y0} is the value of the yield stress at the time when the failure criterion is reached, G_f is the fracture energy per unit area. The material properties of the matrix phase are shown in Table 2.

Parameters	E(GPa)	ν	σ_y (MPa)	ρ (g/cm ³)
Matrix	4.2	0.35	125	980

Table 2: The material properties of the matrix phase

2.2 Finite element model setup

The numerical model was developed using the commercial software Abaqus/explicit. The dynamic explicit analysis was selected due to the complex contact between the drill and the workpiece during drilling. The details of the finite element model are shown in Figure 2.

2.2.1 Geometry and meshing of the drill and workpiece

The diameter of the twist drill used in this paper is equal to 4 mm, and its tip angle is equal to 90°. The tool was assumed to be rigid body to reduce the computational time. 4-node linear tetrahedron elements without element deletion (C3D4 [21]) were used to simulate the drill.

The workpiece contains two plies after simplify, and its stacking sequence is [45/90]. In addition, the outer diameter of the CFRP laminates is 6 mm. In order to improve the computational efficiency, a pre-drilled hole was set on the laminates. Meanwhile, the micro part consists of fiber phase and matrix phase was set on the bottom of each ply of the laminates, and the other part of the workpiece that set to be EHM was the macro part. (It should be noted that, the fiber phase is not representing a single fiber, but a bundle of fibers due to computational constraints.) The workpiece used 8-node linear brick and reduced integration (C3D8R) elements to improve computational efficiency. The element sizes of the fiber phase, matrix phase were smaller than the EHM, and an appropriate balance between accuracy and computational cost was achieved through refining the element size. The aspect ratio of the meshes that around the drill was about 1 to ensure that the meshes would not be distorted during the calculation, and the aspect ratio of the meshes that away from the drill was about 2 to reduce the computational time.

Figure 2: Details of the finite element model

2.2.2 Boundary conditions and drill-workpiece contact

The rotational and translational velocities in Z direction were applied to the drill body as spindle speed (3000 rpm) and feed rate (150 mm/min), respectively. And also, all nodes on the outer diameter of the laminates were fixed to prevent the workpiece from moving.

In this model, a surface-to-surface kinematic contact algorithm was used to simulate the interaction between the tool and the workpiece [22], and a general contact was defined between each ply to avoid penetration. The contact forces were algorithm generated based on the penalty contact method. And the friction coefficient was set equal to 0.3 in the present study based on the previous studies [23-25].

3. MODEL VALIDATION AND RESULTS DISCUSSION

The thrust force and the induced burrs during the CFRP drilling were acquired through the numerical model. And the drilling experiments were performed for validation purpose. In this section, the results were compared between the finite element simulation and the experiments.

3.1. Experimental setup

The CFRP drilling experiments were carried out on the Micron 3-axis machining center, as shown in Figure 3. The toughened T800/3900-2B CFRPs were used in the experiments. Pre-drilled holes were set on the workpiece which was consistent with the numerical model, and the quality of the pre-drilled holes was guaranteed to have no effect on the research. The tool was made of YG8 cemented carbide. the geometry of the tool and the drilling parameters were the same with the numerical model. Kistler 9257B three-component dynamometer was used during drilling to record the cutting forces. And the KEYENCE VH-Z50L microscope helped to photograph the induced damage.

Figure 3: Setup of the drilling experiments

3.2 Validation of the thrust force

The simulate and experimental thrust force in drilling of CFRPs with pre-drilled holes were obtained in this paper, and the filtered thrust forces at the initial stage of the drilling are shown in Figure 4. It is indicated that the thrust force growth along the drilling at the initial stage of the drilling. The growth rate of the thrust force obtained by simulation and experiments are 41N/s and 36N/s respectively, and the deviation of the result is 12% approximately. The precision of the simulation can be improved through the optimization of the finite elements of the workpiece and drill.

Figure 4: The filtered thrust forces at the initial stage of the drilling

3.3 Validation of the burrs

The burrs at the hole wall and outlet of the hole induced by simulation and experiments in drilling of CFRPs are shown in Figure 5. In which, Figure 5A and Figure 5B are respectively the top view of the hole wall and outlet of the hole obtained by simulation; Figure 5C and Figure 5D are respectively the bottom view of the hole wall and outlet of the hole obtained by simulation; Figure 5a and Figure 5b are respectively the top view and bottom view of the hole obtained by experiment.

For the micro part of the model, it can be seen that a lot of burrs were generated at the outlet of the hole. The average length of the burrs obtained by simulation and experiment are 0.58 mm and 0.65 mm respectively, and the difference is around 10%. Meanwhile, there is no burr at the hole wall of the micro part, which is consistent with the experimental results. Therefore, it can be concluded that the burrs induced during the CFRP drilling can be effectively simulated by the numerical model that developed on the microscopic scale. In addition, the reason why the more burrs were induced on the hole exit was also analyzed in this research. During the drilling of the CFRP laminates, there is no support below the material at outlet of the hole, thus the out-of-plane deformation of the mentioned

material occurs easily under the push of the drill. Once the deformation occurs, the material is hard to be removed, which consequently results in the generation of the burrs. However, the material at the hole wall is support by the material below it, which weaken the out-of-plane deformation. Therefore, there is no burr at the hole wall.

For the macro part of the model, it is shown that there is no burr at the hole wall and outlet of the hole. Therefore, the burrs induced during the CFRP drilling can not be simulated by the numerical model that developed on the macroscopic scale. An explanation of it is related to the material assumption. The macro part of the model was developed based on the Equivalent Homogeneous Material assumption, and the constitutive law, failure initiation criteria and damage evolution law of this part are totally the same. Once the stiffness of the elements is degrade to zero, they will be deleted synchronous and no material will be left.

Figure 5: Details of the drilled holes

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a numerical model was developed to simulate the drilling of CFRP laminates on both the macroscopic and microscopic scales. The induced burrs during CFRP drilling were studied through this model. Based on the simulation results that validated by experiments, some key conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- (1) The burrs induced during the CFRP drilling can be effectively simulated by the numerical model that developed on the microscopic scale. But the model developed on the macroscopic scale which based on the Equivalent Homogeneous Material assumption cannot simulate the burring.
- (2) The CFRP drilling induced burrs are easier generated on the hole exit than on the hole wall.

This study provides an effective method for the prediction of the burrs, which is helpful for the optimization of the process parameters and the design of the tool.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to cordially thank the Program for New Century Excellent Talents in University (No. NCET-13-0081), the National Program on Key Basic Research Project (No. 2014CB046503) and National Innovation Group (No. 51321004) for its financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Santiuste, X. Soldani and M.H. Miguélez, Machining FEM model of long fiber composites for aeronautical components, *Composite Structures*, **92**, 2010, pp. 691-698.
- [2] D. Che, I. Saxena, P. Han, P. Guo and K.F. Ehmann, Machining of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics/Polymers: A Literature Review, *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, **136**, 2014, pp. 1-22.
- [3] R. Chinmaya, Dandekar and Y.C. Shin, Modeling of machining of composite materials: A review, *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, **57**, 2012, pp. 102-121.

- [4] U.A. Khashaba, Drilling of polymer matrix composites: A review, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **47**, 2013, pp. 1817-1832.
- [5] A.M. Abrao, P.E. Faria, J.C. Campos Rubio, P. Reis and J. Paulo Davim, Drilling of fiber reinforced plastics: A review, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **186**, 2007, pp. 1-7.
- [6] C.K.H. Dharan and M.S. Won, Machining parameters for an intelligent machining system for composite laminates, *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, **40**, 2000, pp. 415-426.
- [7] D. Iliescu, D. Gehin, I. Iordanoff, F. Girot and M.E. Gutiérrez, A discrete element method for the simulation of CFRP cutting, *Composites Science and Technology*, **70**, 2010, pp. 73-80.
- [8] O. Isbilir and E. Ghassemieh, Delamination and wear in drilling of carbon-fiber reinforced plastic composites using multilayer TiAlN/TiN PVD-coated tungsten carbide tools, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **31**, 2012, pp. 717-727.
- [9] X. Soldani, C. Santiuste, A. Muñoz-Sánchez and M.H. Miguélez, Influence of tool geometry and numerical parameters when modeling orthogonal cutting of LFRP composites, *Composites: Part A*, **42**, 2011, pp. 1205-1216.
- [10] C. Santiust, H. Miguélez and X. Soldani, Out-of-plane failure mechanisms in LFRP composite cutting, *Composite Structures*, **93**, 2011, pp. 2706-2713.
- [11] O. Isbilir and E. Ghassemieh, Finite element analysis of drilling of carbon fibre reinforced composites, *Appl Compos Mater*, **19**, 2012, pp. 637-656.
- [12] O. Isbilir and E. Ghassemieh, Numerical investigation of the effects of drill geometry on drilling induced delamination of carbon fiber reinforced composites, *Composite Structures*, **105**, 2013, pp. 126-133.
- [13] V. Phadnis, F. Makhdum, A. Roy and V. Silberschmidt, Drilling induced damage in CFRP laminates: experimental and numerical analysis, *Solid State Phenomena*, **188**, 2012, pp. 150-157.
- [14] V. Phadnis, F. Makhdum, A. Roy and V. Silberschmidt, Drilling in carbon/epoxy composites: experimental investigations and finite element implementation, *Composites: Part A*, **47**, 2013, pp. 41-51.
- [15] N. Feito, J. López-Puente, C. Santiuste and M.H. Miguélez, Numerical prediction of delamination in CFRP drilling, *Composite Structures*, **108**, 2014, pp. 677-683.
- [16] N. Feito, J. Diaz-Álvarez, J. López-Puente and M.H. Miguélez, Numerical analysis of the influence of tool wear and special cutting geometry when drilling woven CFRPs, *Composite Structures*, **138**, 2016, pp. 285-294.
- [17] C. Murphy, G. Byrne and M.D. Gilchrist, The performance of coated tungsten carbide drills when machining carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy composite materials, *Institution of Mechanical Engineers*, **216**, 2002, pp. 143-152.
- [18] G. Poulachon, J. Outeiro, C. Ramirez, V. Andréa and G. Abrivard, Hole surface topography and tool wear in CFRP drilling, *3rd CIRP Conference on Surface Integrity, Charlotte, USA, June 8-10, 2016*, Procedia CIRP, Paper 45, 2016, pp. 35-38.
- [19] F. Wang, B. Qian, Z. Jia, R. Fu and D. Cheng, Secondary cutting edge wear of one-shot drill bit in drilling CFRP and its impact on hole quality, *Composite Structures*, 2017, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.04.024>
- [20] L. Yang, Y. Yan and N. Kuang, Experimental and numerical investigation of aramid fibre reinforced laminates subjected to low velocity impact, *Polymer Testing*, **32**, 2013, pp. 1163-1173.
- [21] Dassault Systèmes, Abaqus/CAE User's Guide, 2015.
- [22] C. Hortig and B. Svendsen, Simulation of chip formation during high-speed cutting, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **186**, 2007, pp. 66-76.
- [23] D. Arola and M. Ramulu, Orthogonal cutting of fiber-reinforced composites: a finite element analysis, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, **39**, 1997, pp. 597-613.
- [24] G.V.G. Rao, P. Mahajan and N. Bhatnagar, Micro-mechanical modeling of machining of FRP composites cutting force analysis, *Composites Science and Technology*, **67**, 2007, pp. 579-593.
- [25] L. Lasri, M. Nouari and M.E. Mansori, Modelling of chip separation in machining unidirectional FRP composites by stiffness degradation concept, *Composites Science and Technology*, **69**, 2009, pp. 684-692.